

INTEGRATING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSEUMS

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Ipak yo'li turizm va madaniy meros xalqaro universiteti dosenti

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada virtual reallik, kengaytirilgan reallik, proyeksiyali xaritalash va boshqalar kabi innovatsiyon texnologiyalarning muzeylar va madaniy meros ob'ektlarida integratsiyalashuvi, jadal rivojlanishi va korgazmalarining muhim qismiga aylanishi, dunyo boylab olim va tadqiqotchilarning bu boradagi ukarning foydasi va qadri haqidgi fikrlari o'rganiladi. Shuningdek, jamiyat va muzeylarni mana shunday zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan jozibador, rang-barang, zayqli va uzoq muddatli ta'lim bilan bog'lash hamda multimedia uskunalari yordamida muzey muhitiga jalb etish orqali yangi tashrif buturuvchilar sonini ko'paytirish, ob'ektlarning qiymati va chuqur tarixini ko'rsatadigan proyektorlar, audio qollanmalar, sensorli ekranlar, 3D ekranlar va boshqa uskunalarni jalb etish vazifasiga yonaltirilgan.*

***Abstract.** This thesis researches the history of integrating innovative technologies, such as Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Projection mapping and etc., in museums and cultural heritage sites, the rapid development and becoming them as the significant part of exhibitions, opinions of scientists and researchers about them on benefits and values among the World. It is also aimed to connecting the society and museums with these kinds of modern technologies for education in attractive, colorful, enjoyable and long-time way and enlarging the number of new visitors by involving them to the museum atmosphere with the help of multimedia equipments, like projectors, audio guides, touch screens, 3D screens and etc, which demonstrate the objects value and deep history.*

***Key words:** 3D screen, AR, VR, museum education, intellect, multimedia.*

One of the significant issues for several decades in museum collection was unavailability of materials for analyzing and doing research. Indoor spaces of buildings only exhibited the physical collection of objects. The invention of technology that was able to digitize collections, is radically changing and reshaping the core missions of museums, which includes preservation, making catalogue, developing and providing the access. Nowadays, people are getting access to almost any kind of sources in digital form through websites and official web-pages of museums, where are used four emerging models of digital images of artworks: online display, proprietary image licensing, open licensing and user-generated art images. For example, virtual museums, online exhibitions, Commercial stock agencies, Amico Artstor, Wikipedia and others.

As Gretchen Sorin(2000) states: " The contents of most history museum storage room do not reflect the full record of the nation's past. History museums need to go further to identify artifacts related to groups whose history is not part of the written record", museums are able to collaborate the history and artifacts through attaching intangible site of heritage.

Tomas and Brown, 2001, believed that the 21 century will make opportunity to move information and knowledge easily that also will be cheap and accessable anybody without social or locational barriers. Kaytee Smith shares the experience about The North Caroline Museum of Natural Science' programs, which is able to teach twenty-first-century skills appropriate for all-ages. Furthermore, Jannifer A.Scot of Jane Addams Hull-Home Museum clarified the project,

Making the West Side: Community Conservations on Neighbourhood Change, where were discussed public programs in the field of history museum and its role on social changes.

The whole history and its surrounding features is becoming digital, the significant reason of this process is inventing the Internet in 1970s and its rapid spread to almost any sphere of society. Museums generates the process of learning via involving digital technologies in two ways: onsite with the help of various digital interactives and online through creating widespread websites that get more popularity than the museum themselves. Originally, on July 1994, the first United Kingdom (UK) Museum Website was created and activated by the Natural History Museum. As soon as 2002 was the grandiose period when the amount of virtual visitors to museums' websites were rapidly increased several times that had already overwhelmed the number of on-site visitors. This fact proves that websites of museums were able to attract visitors, diverse the interest, and also spread knowledge more than museums buildings, Although until 1999, UK museum education system was used to conduct tours, that combined audio-visual guides as well as printed materials, without attaching the websites.

The original purpose of making museum websites was as a method of promotion in order to advertise the whole heritage and its uniqueness with the help of full description, pictures and useful information so that interested visitors could find need able data related to museum collections, besides use them for their research and education. The first steps of making this process accessible in museums is creating the programs for analyzing the texts, maps and models, like "Corpus Linguistics", "Geographical Information Systems"(GIS) and "Topic Modeling".

The starting point of engaging the huge diversity of tools was making effective interactions between visitors and displays. The result of Falk et al in 2004 research underlined the lasting influence of interactive approach on visitors. Besides, the founding director of The Road, Joanne Heyler explained her viewpoint according the physical museum as the need of visitors and the role of Visitor Services Associates. Additionally, Charlotte Martin, museum educator for access programs at Intrepid Sea, Air and Space Museum, demonstrates accessibility of museums for every audience with physical, emotional and intellectual needs. Moreover, Sung et al, 2008, studied the use of electronic guidebook devices by museums as the beneficial equipment with supplemental information, which are used in further informal learning. The design of guidebooks was focused on the audio-visual and the scenario -based approaches, where the main goal was providing the interest to spend more time at exhibit through motivating them with the help of references, reports in a certain frequency and sequency by using the guidebooks.

In modern versions of displaying historical exhibitions is collaborating with innovative technologies as Augmented Reality (AR), Aurasma, Junaio, Talking Objects and others that increases educational experiences of visitors (Appendix 1).Christiane Paul notes in her book Digital Art : "technologies often... develop faster than the rhetoric evaluating them"(Paul, 2008:67). The initial tool was AR, created by overlaying a computer generated image,that was the fundamental layer for others.

Augmented Reality is a type of technology that integrates the virtual media content, like graphics, animations, and videos, with the real surrounding in order to come into life the collections. Geoffrey Alan Rhodes, Filmmaker, Assistant professor at School of the Art Institute of Chicago, states "AR is an attractive medium for use in museums because digital databases challenge existing archives with obsolescence, and the ever-growing tide of digital information can be reconciled with traditional, physical databases through the promise of AR". The reason of getting global trend in using by various spheres that is increasing year by year is a

life view of any elements, augmented by computer-generated images, that are based on four senses of human, like sight, sound, feel, and smell. It was able to become a personalized mobile guide for discovery-based learning. In modern world, almost all kind of museums are trying to integrate different versions of equipments and technologies, starting from simple until innovative, in their managing system. Commonly, they are classified into several categories according their way of demonstrating:

—the world wide web or more precisely websites or web pages that supplies access to digital resources and materials, like online libraries, journals, datas, virtual exhibitions or virtual museums with the help of interest surfing.

—multimedia tools that provides access to graphics, pictures, photographs, archive animations or films, videos and sound as a background effect for diversifying learning process.

—computer mediated conferencing, like discussion boards or chat rooms that includes discussive and collaborative activities, also e-mail system for communicating with museum staff

—presentation technologies, like digital projectors for making the visit more interactive and engageable.

—simulations and models that makes available the process of interaction with and manipulation of the real world. This includes different kinds of experiments, trips and interactive activities related to museum collections and making research.

— micro-world and game that include educational scenarios for extension of visitors knowledge. In these kinds of games, participants will feel themselves as a part of actions related to museum exhibitions rather than the simple observer.

—streaming digital audio and video tools which are represented through gadgets and tablets via the applications to real environment.

—visualization techniques that demonstrate the complex set of data through full visual way.

In the study process, there were described clearly and broadly the history of development innovative technologies through museums around the World, the purpose, type and role of modern equipments with detailed explanations, besides the experiments of foreign museum institutions and their analytical results in order to collaborate with them in the way of integrating to Uzbek museums.

Museum collaboration with government, related organizations and institutions, IT specialists, surrounding society and international organizations, partnership institutions can be an opportunity for further development in the way of creating new and modern, fast applications, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, digital data and storages, virtual exhibitions and museums, new social networks and web pages and etc.

In the nearest future, I believe we will have new occasions for representing our culture and history in new images and ways through the World. And any person from different parts of society will know Uzbekistan as a center of Cultural Heritage with full of historical artifacts, which have significant value in Central Asia as well as the greatest Silk Road.

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